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ICT Challenges and Opportunities in Development of Afghanistan

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Abstract: The term information and communication technologies (ICTs) encompass the range of technologies for gathering, storing, retrieving, processing, analyzing, and transmitting information that are essential to prospering in a globalized economy. Advances in ICTs have reduced the costs of managing information and introduced innovations in products, processes, and organizational structures that, in turn, have generated new ways of working, market development, and livelihood practices. Internationally, Advanced countries attaches to ICTs as enablers of economic, governance, security, education, healthcare, and social well-being reconstruction and development. While there is little doubt that ICTs are an engine for social and economic development, quantifying their impact is difficult. Evidence remains largely anecdotal, and the link between ICT deployment and reconstruction and development remains vague.

Since the people of Afghanistan are lagging behind the caravan of technology and progress and have an urgent need to use technology in various fields of development and construction of the country, this study shows that the strategic use of information and ICTs can increase significantly the likelihood of success in Afghanistan's affected-nation, cross-sector reconstruction and development. Moreover, the combination of technology, information content, and people schooled in the use of each will reshape enterprises and activities and will end to a significant advancement all across the country. Finally, highlighted overview of Afghanistan the country and the ICT environment infrastructure, skill base, and implementation challenges and some of the related coordination and information sharing challenges.

Keywords: ICT, Challenges, Opportunities, Development, Afghanistan.

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Introduction

ICT can be a powerful enabler of reconstruction and development goals. It is both a sector and an enabler of cross-sector reconstruction and development. As a sector, ICT supports national capacity building and export market focus and plays a critical role in reestablishing basic economic linkages by relieving communication bottlenecks from financial, governmental, and cultural information flows. As an enabler, it supports global positioning focus and adoption of cross-sector strategies that can be used to harness the uniqueness of ICT to accelerate a wider reconstruction and development process. It is also an essential enabler for boosting productivity by helping to establish a climate for job creation, investment, and sustainable growth.

The real benefits lie not in the provision of technology per se, but rather in promoting creation of powerful social and economic networks by dramatically improving communications and the exchange of information. ICT activities supporting stabilization, reconstruction, and development operations in an affected nation can be problematic.

Real world experience suggests that ICT can be (and is being) used to generate social, economic, cultural, and political changes, but, as noted earlier, it is difficult to quantify the impact of ICT initiatives and separate the influence of ICT from that of other factors, such as civil security stability, governance, or economic growth. Furthermore, internationally agreed indicators to measure and compare country experiences are lacking. Some countries are certainly doing much better in exploiting ICTs and adopting more effective ICT policies and strategies than others, but there is no agreed and uniform way to measure and compare.

Afghanistan is one of the world's poorest and least developed nations. Because of years of fighting, roads, power, water, telecommunications, healthcare, and education have been disrupted or are dysfunctional.

The intent of this research is to raise awareness of the importance of the role of ICT in development and follow-on reconstruction and development. Afghanistan is used as a case study to examine and highlight, opportunities and the challenges encountered in trying to rebuild a war-torn country's telecommunications and IT infrastructure and to use it to enable other sector reconstruction and development.

Examining the current situation of ICT

In spite of overwhelming challenges like political instability, poverty, economical problem and lockage of national policies/strategies, Afghan ICT has proven to be a major success growing from essentially nothing to over 15 million subscribers since 2001. The ICT sector has created implemented many national projects and created infrastructures, developed systems, stepped to electronic government, generated more foreign investment, high-quality jobs (eighter in private and public sectors), and new tax revenue than any other legitimate sector.

Although significant progress has been made in the Telecommunications and IT sector in Afghanistan, and it has truly been the "success story" emerging out of the recovery of a country left dysfunctional from 43 years of war. Progress towards bridging the digital divide and moving Afghanistan into the 21st century information age has not been accidental but is largely due to having the right people at the right place with the right vision, energy, and expertise to make reasonable decisions and take actions to make things happen.

Afghanistan ICT success was and continues to be enabled by a number of factors:

- 1) A GOA understanding of the importance of ICT as an engine of economic development and its role as an enabler of cross-sector reconstruction.
- 2) Early GOA establishment of ICT policies, regulations, laws, and a regulatory authority.
- 3) MCIT vision, strategy, and plan for moving Afghanistan ICT into the 21st century.

- 4) Information age supported at the highest level of government.
- 5) Establishment of a good public-private partnership that enabled private ICT investments and rapid growth of their networks.
- 6) International community support
- 7) Placed early emphasis on ICT capacity building, including the establishment of professional educational institutions, training facilities, and capabilities
- 8) Willingness to invest in and support Afghan MCIT creation of a national telecommunications and IT network.
- 9) Recognizing ICT as an engine of economic development.
- 10) Elevate ICT investment priorities to be equivalent to roads, power, and water.
- 11) Improve understanding of affected-nation information and related ICT business cultures.
- 12) MCIT should develop a strategy, architecture, and enhancement plan for a robust, national, long-distance network and backbone infrastructure to enhance Afghan ICT coverage, access, services, and performance.

Opportunities

Much remains to be done to make Afghanistan ICT a viable and robust network to effectively support civil security, governance, economic growth, healthcare, and education. A discussion of gaps and shortfalls and some thoughts on actions that could be taken to overcome them and help realize the network's full potential follows. The Afghan ICT network is growing and becoming more robust. ICT capacity building some steps taken but much remains to be done. Some important defects still exist:

- 1) ICT infrastructure and processes are not adequately protected against cyber and physical threats.
- 2) Nationwide coverage, service quality, and capacity has been marginal but improving with increased competition.
- 3) Cost of services is very high than neighboring countries.
- 4) Reliable infrastructure (Fiber connectivity and power) is lacking for ICT.
- 5) Data services and access are inadequate to support e-Solutions.

Challenges

- 1) There are no approved and legal policies and strategies on systemization and use of technologies.
- 2) absence of a functioning team as well as laws, regulations, and enforcement mechanisms; widespread unemployment and poverty; and a shortage of leaders, managers, administrators, and technical personnel with 21st-century information and ICT management, operations, and technical skills.
- 3) lack of adequate understanding of the affected-nation information culture and ICT business culture.
- 4) There is no clear mapping of responding stakeholder organizations roles and responsibilities.
- 5) Program development, project coordination, information sharing, and ICT implementation are largely uncoordinated and non-standard.
- 6) No agreed architecture or plan is in place for affected nation ICT reconstruction.
- 7) A coherent civil-military ICT strategy and plan for responding-nation civilian elements, international organizations (IOs), and nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) is also lacking.
- 8) No agreed mechanisms or procedures are in place to enable effective civil-military coordination and information sharing among participants and with the affected nation. Interveners consistently do not view ICT as a reconstruction and development priority equal to roads, power, and water or as an enabler of cross-sector reconstruction and development.
- 9) Consequently, senior leadership has no framework to make investment decisions and track ICT-related reconstruction and development progress.

Conclusion

Study findings implies that ICT has been an enabler for developing the Afghan government, economy, and social well-being. While there have been successes, challenges remain. Continued smart investments and use of information and ICT will serve to further enhance government capacity, legitimacy, and transparency, help reduce corruption, increase economic growth, and support social stability. It is certainly a key to being successful in Afghanistan. A word of caution must be issued, however, now that the ICT sector in Afghanistan has been relatively successful and appears to be operating reasonably well on its own initiative, there may be a desire on the part of government and other sectors that have not been as successful. Such a shift without careful consideration of not only first order but second and third order effects could have significant unintended consequences, especially if the ICT sector is not yet prepared to truly sustain operations on its own without the support and attention of the international community. Consideration of such a shift in international and government support needs to be carefully assessed, monitored, and managed over time to ensure informed choices and decision are made and that progress continues to bridge the digital divide and move Afghanistan into the information society of the 21st century.

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